

Weed Identification in Rice Cultivation Employing Semantic Segmentation

Neha¹, Manisha Agarwal², Seema Verma³, Manisha Jailia⁴

Department of Computer Science, Banasthali Vidyapith, Niwai, India^{1, 2, 4}
National Institute of Technical Teacher's Training and Research, Bhopal, India³

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Abstract

Weed detection is a crucial task in precision agriculture, as it enables farmers to take targeted measures to control weeds and reduce crop losses. In this paper, an attention-enhanced SegNet model is used in a deep learning-based weed detection method. Images of paddy fields are used to train the network to segregate weeds at the pixel level. In order to identify weeds, this research compares the SegNet architecture with an improved SegNet model that incorporates attention techniques. SegNet serves as a baseline encoder–decoder network, while the SegNet-Attention model incorporates attention gates to emphasize relevant spatial features and suppress background noise. Standard performance criteria, including accuracy, precision, recall, intersection over union (IoU), and dice coefficient, were used to train and assess both models on a dataset of weed images. According to experimental data, the SegNet-Attention model consistently outperforms the standard SegNet by enhancing weed boundary delineation and segmentation accuracy, especially in complicated field scenarios with overlapping crops and different lighting conditions. In comparison to traditional SegNet designs, experimental research shows that the attention-enhanced SegNet model delivers improved segmentation accuracy and robustness, especially in complicated image settings. These findings demonstrate the applicability of the suggested method for high-precision semantic segmentation applications by showing increased segmentation accuracy and robustness when compared to traditional encoder–decoder models.

Keywords: Rice field, Precision agriculture, Weed detection, Semantic segmentation, Segnet-attention

1. Introduction

In India and many other countries such as China, Japan, Thailand, Sri Lanka, etc., Paddy is one of the most vital crops. Although paddy is cultivated throughout most parts of India, its productivity and yield are very low. This is primarily due to weeds and improper weed management systems. By vying with weeds for light, nutrients, and moisture in paddy fields, they reduce the amount of rice produced [1]. Therefore, a variety of traditional techniques were applied to manage weed growth and boost yields. In India, hand weeding, machine weeding, and the use of pesticides are the common methods for managing weeds. Using a sickle, hoe, or spade, or by pulling the weeds by their roots, is the process of hand weeding. The task of hand weeding requires a lot of labor and time. Thus, manual weeding is not recommended due to the shortage of labourers and the high cost of labor [2]. This labor-intensive process raises production costs in regions with high labor expenses. A rotary weeder is the equipment used for mechanical weeding. They might not do well in every kind of field. For instance, the conditions can be difficult in paddy fields. The rotary weeder may find it difficult to perform its tasks due to the damp soil and the way rice is planted.

Around the world, weeds are controlled by applying chemical sprays either before or after they emerge. The effectiveness of these chemical weed management technologies has outperformed mechanical approaches in reducing weed densities [3]. Herbicides are versatile and inexpensive, but they also have a lot of negative effects, especially given the serious problem of herbicide resistance in weeds [4]. The primary disadvantages emerge from the traditional spraying technique, which can result in the overuse of herbicides and pose significant risks to the environment, ecological and safety concerns and pollution[5]. On the other hand, Precision Agriculture (PA) aims need-based site-specific application of chemicals[6]. Advanced target identification and automatic control technologies are combined in precision spraying to precisely apply herbicides only to plants or regions that need weed control[7]. In order to precisely spray at the identified target sites, it is necessary to first employ machine vision, remote sensing, and other technologies to identify and locate field targets in real-time. The spraying device is then controlled by the navigation control system.

In the field of precision agriculture weed identification, semantic segmentation has become increasingly popular in recent years. Pixel-by-pixel classification of objects is known as Semantic Segmentation. Semantic segmentation (SS) is a pixel-level classification problem that has transformed several domains such as, precision agriculture [8] and medical image segmentation [9]. SegNet [10] is a deep fully convolutional neural network that was first proposed by Cambridge and is used to segment images. In order to gather multi-scale information, SegNet uses the symmetric codec structure and index structure of max pooling, which has a higher precision and lower computational cost than FCN. This work proposes a semantic segmentation technique to classify images. We trained SegNet with two different backbones, VGG16 and VGG19.

The remaining part of this work is distributed into five sections. Sections 2 present the related work. Section 3 discusses the methodology for weed detection using semantic segmentation, dataset. Experimental results were discussed in section 4. Lastly, conclusion was presented for this proposed work.

2. Related Work

One crucial topic of study is the detection of weed density and location [11]. With the use of computer vision and image processing techniques, we are able to obtain estimates of the amount and distribution of weeds in a field. These estimates can then be used as a basis for treating weeds appropriately. Creating a sprayer that can automatically saturate weedy patches in crops is an intriguing application [12]. Maximizing output (crop yield) while minimizing input (fertilizer, pesticides, herbicides, etc.) during the crop-growing process is the essence of precision agriculture. In order to create sustainable agricultural operations, precision agriculture advancements are crucial. The main difficulties associated with this field of study include erratic field conditions, variable weather that can impact the dataset, variations in lighting [13], and the fact that weeds and crops have different morphologies, colors, and textures that change significantly as they grow.

Potena et al., [14], Segment and classify image pixels into crop and weeds using two separate CNNs. To extract the pixels that indicate projections of 3D points that belong to green vegetation, a lightweight convolutional neural network (CNN) is employed to carry out a fast and accurate pixel-by-pixel binary image segmentation. The extracted pixels are subsequently divided into the crop and weed classes using a deeper CNN.

Inkyu et al., [15] uses multispectral images of sugar beet and weeds, captured by a micro aerial vehicle (MAV) to classify dense semantic weeds using an encoder-decoder cascaded convolutional neural network, or SegNet. Train six models with varying input channels, then

condition (fine-tune) each model to achieve classification metrics of 0.78 area under the curve (AUC) and ~0.8 F1-score.

Amin Nasiri et al., [16] deployed UNet with ResNet50 architecture to distinguish sugar beetroot, weed, and soil using pixel wise segmentation technique. A model utilizing the custom loss function and the dataset structure for training produced an accuracy and intersection over union (IoU) score of 0.8423 and 0.9606, respectively.

Xu Ma et al., [17] proposed the SegNet model which uses RGB colour images of Rice field. The RGB colour images were labelled the pixels manually to generate ground truth images to separate them in three categories mainly, rice seedlings, weeds and background. The results of proposed method were compared with FCN and UNet. The suggested SegNet approach successfully classified the background, weeds, and rice seedling pixels in the paddy field images with an improved classification accuracy of 92.7%.

Radhika Kamath et al., [18] uses three semantic segmentation techniques such as, SegNet, UNet and Pyramid Scene Parsing Network (PSPNet) to classify two types of weeds mainly sedges and broadleaf weeds. This study uses two types of dataset, first dataset consist only weed type images and the second one consists images of paddy field and weeds. Playment.io tool was used to annotate the images and each pixel was assigned as one of the classes among four classes. The PSPNet was outperformed with mean IoU around 70% to 80% and frequency weighted IoU is 80% to 90%.

In order to solve issues like color similarity and fluctuating environmental conditions, **Jiaheng Zhang et al.**, [19] develops a weed recognition model for maize fields using an enhanced Swin-UNet. Semantic segmentation is used to distinguish maize seedlings from weeds, and a Swin transformer module is used to improve performance. To increase the model's capacity for generalization, DropBlock regularization is applied. The model is evaluated in comparison with the original Swin-UNet, Mask R-CNN, PSANet and DeepLabv3. Original Swin-UNet outperforms the others with the value of mean Intersection over Union and mean pixel accuracy of 92.72% and 95.57% respectively.

3. Methodology

3.1 Dataset preparation

Study Site

The research site is situated in Deoli in the Kota district of India (25.0014 N, 76.1173 E). The study site consists of rice fields which are also covered with weeds.

Data Collection

The dataset consists of 3,360 multispectral images of size 1920px x 1080px acquired with Phantom P4 drone. This unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) has been selected for data gathering because it features an integrated satellite positioning system that allows the UAV to be located both latitude and longitude. The Phantom P4 drone has a GPS/GLONASS satellite navigation system, a FOV94 20mm, f/2.8 focus lens, and an effective pixel count of 12.4 million. Figure 1 shows the image of rice field.

Figure1: Weed Seedling in Rice field

There are total 3,360 images of rice field and their corresponding ground-truth images. Among which 2,352 images were used to train the model and remaining 1,008 images were used to test the model. The dataset was split into training and testing datasets in a 70:30 ratio to ensure efficient use of the data. The proposed model's resilience and segmentation performance were assessed using the testing dataset, while the training dataset was utilized to train the model. Table1 depicts the distribution of images.

Table1: Distribution of paddy field dataset			
	Train	Test	Total
Rice field dataset	2,352	1,008	3,360

3.2Data Annotation

In order to manually label each pixel in our self-constructed dataset with semantic information at the pixel level and provide the ground truth (GT) images needed for the segmentation model, utilized the VGG-annotator software. The outputs of this annotation are segmentation masks, which provide the precise shape and boundaries of each weed in an image, pixel by pixel. Fig. 2 presents samples of original and GT images, with weeds in white and the remaining part of the image is rice crops which are in black.

Figure2: Images of rice field (a) sample images of dataset (b) Ground-truth image

3.3 Segmentation model

FCNN architecture is the foundation of SegNet[10]. The segmentation method uses an encoder and decoder followed by a pixel-wise classification layer. Its purpose is to take an image as an input and generates a pixel-wise label map. Using a sequence of convolutional and pooling layers, the encoder extracts high-level features. Next comes the decoder, which upsamples and creates a segmentation map using the spatial pooling indices produced during the max-pooling in the encoder phase. This type of up-sampling preserves the fine-grained information in the output while still being memory-efficient. In this work, SegNet was used, one of the semantic segmentation models to improve performance and accuracy. Figure3 shows the architecture of SegNet.

Figure3: Architecture of SegNet[10]

The modified SegNet-style encoder-decoder architecture combined with attention gates for better semantic segmentation is the foundation of the suggested methodology. The network has a symmetric architecture with a decoder for spatial reconstruction and a deep convolutional encoder for feature extraction. Attention methods are used to refine skip links between related encoder and decoder stages in order to highlight relevant spatial features. Figure4 shows the architecture of SegNet-Attention with Attention guided skip-connections.

3.3.1 Encoder Network

The encoder is made up of several convolutional blocks, each of which has two convolutional layers with a 3x3 kernel. Batch normalization and ReLU activation come next. Hierarchical feature representations are gradually extracted from the input image via these layers. After every encoder block, max-pooling layers with a 2x2 pool size are added to increase the receptive field while decreasing spatial dimensions. In order to maintain high-level semantic information at the bottleneck layer, the final encoder block functions without pooling.

3.3.2 Attention Gate Mechanism

Attention gates are presented to improve feature selection in skip connections. The skip feature map from the encoder and the gating signal from the decoder are the two inputs that each attention gate gets. To match dimensionality, 1x1 convolutional layers are used to convert both inputs. An attention map is created by adding the altered features, passing them

through ReLU activation, then another 1x1 convolution and a sigmoid activation. By multiplying this attention map by the encoder feature map element-wise, the network is able to suppress unimportant areas and concentrate on important spatial information.

3.3.3 Decoder Network

The decoder uses up-sampling operations to restore the feature maps' spatial resolution. The relevant attention-refined skip connection and the up-sampled feature map are concatenated at each decoding stage. Two convolutional layers with batch normalization and ReLU activation are utilized to further process this fused representation. The decoder preserves semantic consistency while gradually restoring spatial features.

3.3.4 Output Layer

The decoded feature maps are mapped to the required number of segmentation classes using a 1x1 convolution in the final layer. Multi-class semantic segmentation is made possible by generating pixel-wise class probabilities using a softmax activation function.

Figure4: Architecture of SegNet-Attention with Attention guided skip-connections.

4. Experimental results

Tensorflow and Keras were used to implement the suggested SegNet-Attention model. Every experiment used RGB images that had been scaled to 256 x 256 pixels. The Adam optimizer was used to train the network with categorical cross-entropy loss and an initial learning rate of 0.001. After every convolutional layer, batch normalization was used to enhance convergence and lessen overfitting. A predetermined number of epochs were used to train the model, with early stopping determined by validation loss. To improve generalization performance, data augmentation methods like rotation, flipping, and scaling were used.

4.1 Evaluation metrics

Simple accuracy in semantic segmentation models does not provide a whole picture because of the huge class imbalance. To overcome this issue, Intersection over Union (IOU), Dice Coefficient, Precision, and Recall was used in this study. The intersection of the ground truth and the predicted segmentation divided by the area of union between the ground truth and the predicted segmentation is called the intersection over union (IoU), or Jaccard Index. Equation1 describes the formulation of IoU. Equation2 describes the Accuracy of a model.

$$IoU = \frac{\text{Area of overlap}}{\text{Area of intersection}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Dice coefficient} = 2 * \frac{|A \cap B|}{(|A| + |B|)} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (5)$$

Here, the percentage of rice crop occurrences that the model correctly predicted is shown by TP, which stands for True Positive. FP denotes the False Positive that indicates the proportion of rice crop that are incorrectly identified as weeds. The percentage of weed images classified as rice crops is denoted as FN, or False Negative. TN or True Negative indicates the number percentage of weed images that are accurately predicted by the model.

4.2 Result Analysis

The efficiency of the suggested SegNet-Attention model in pixel-level segmentation of images was assessed using a variety of quantitative and qualitative indicators. Using the Adam [20] optimizer with a learning rate of 1×10^{-4} , the model was trained for 50 epochs with a batch size of 8. To improve segmentation accuracy and alleviate class imbalance, a mixed loss function was used. A held-out test set was used for evaluation, and 20% of the training data was set aside for validation.

Table2: Performance evaluation of SegNet-Attention in testing phase

Metrics(in %)	Model Name	
	SegNet	SegNet-Attention
Accuracy	91.84	92.36
Precision	91.84	92.36
Recall	91.50	92.36
IOU	84.68	85.74
Dice-coefficient	91.61	92.28

The SegNet-Attention model exhibits superior segmentation performance, attaining elevated scores in pixel-level accuracy and region overlap metrics (IOU and Dice coefficient). The model appears to be well-balanced, with no discernible bias toward over-segmentation or under-segmentation, based on the similar values for accuracy, precision, and recall.

Figure5: Illustration of SegNet-Attention model performance metrics (a) Recall (b) IOU (c) Precision (d) Accuracy

(c) (d)
Figure6: Illustration of SegNet model performance metrics (a) Recall (b) IOU (c) Precision (d) Accuracy

The baseline SegNet and the improved SegNet-Attention models are compared using Recall, Intersection over Union (IoU), Precision, and Accuracy metrics over training epochs in Figure 5 and Figure 6. In comparison to the traditional SegNet architecture, the SegNet-Attention model exhibits better learning stability and overall performance. Even though both models learn quickly at first, the SegNet-Attention model shows better generalization and less overfitting since it converges more quickly and keeps the difference between the training and validation curves for recall, accuracy, and IoU less. Inconsistent statistical predictions and sensitivity to background noise are reflected in the baseline SegNet's validation IoU and precision curves, which exhibit increased variance and discernible oscillations over epochs. The SegNet-Attention model, on the other hand, achieves smoother convergence with less epoch-to-epoch oscillations, indicating improved border localization and feature discrimination.

5. Conclusion

This work offers a thorough analysis of a SegNet-based VGG16 model using various batch sizes and optimizers, providing important information about how these factors affect the performance of semantic segmentation. The paddy field image dataset was created using phantom p4 drone. The annotation was done by VGG annotator tool. The aggregate findings suggest that deep learning-based semantic segmentation of weeds and rice crops can be applied to safe food production through sustainable site-specific weed management. In terms of accuracy, precision, recall, IoU, and dice coefficient, experimental results show that the SegNet-Attention model performs better than the baseline SegNet, especially in complicated field situations with overlapping crops and variable illumination. The enhanced segmentation quality and convergence behaviour demonstrate how reliable the suggested method is. These findings show that the suggested approach is appropriate for precision agriculture applications, allowing precise and location-specific weed control. In the future, we will compare the performance of our dataset with other paddy field datasets by using different semantic segmentation models.

6. References

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